

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MGNREGS BENEFICIARIES IN VIZAINAGARAM DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of this chapter is to examine the economic activities and evaluate the socio-economic status of the participants in Vizianagaram district, recognized (identified) as one of the top-performing districts in implementing MGNREGS in the state of Andhra Pradesh. Factors such as age, gender, literacy, religion, and caste play a significant role in the participation of households in MGNREGS, as discussed either in this study. This chapter also addresses matters concerning the Physical quality of life of the Participants, including housing conditions, sanitation, and social practices of households. As mentioned earlier, for the purpose of the study 180 sample respondents are selected. Of the total sample respondents, 60 respondents are selected from each mandal, Badangi (60), Ramabhadrapuram (60) and Makkuva (60) in Vizianagaram district.

Keywords: Education, Agriculture, landholding, Drinking water, livelihood and MGNREGS

Introduction

Through giving impoverished individuals access to the official banking system, MGNREGS also started the biggest financial inclusion initiative in history. The implications of this have not yet been assessed by financial management experts. Almost 5 crore savings bank accounts have been opened with post offices and banks across the country. States like Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Uttaranchal, Kerala, and Himachal Pradesh only use deposits in savings bank accounts for all MGNREGS employees, whereas states like Orissa, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan have made great progress in providing banking services to rural residents who are impoverished.

Even though the globe contests the effects of climate change, many rural development experts have characterized MGNREGS as an approach that can assist minimize these effects. According to the latest data, MGNREGS has funded an incredible 20.44 lakh projects, mostly pertaining to water conservation, of which 7.16 lakh have been finished. Given the abundance of literature on water conservation and preservation, Richard Mahapatra (2009), a Delhi-based development writer, asserts that MGNREGS will surely have an impact on agricultural

productivity over time.

The primary goal of rural development is social and economic advancement for rural residents, particularly to enhance their quality of life over time by increasing their income and access to social amenities. People's economic status, which is based on their duties, rights, and opportunities to participate in economic activities, is intimately linked to their social standing. People's economic standing is increasingly seen as a measure of social and societal advancement. But not every advancement leads to an improvement in people's economic activity. The dominant social norms have an impact on people's behaviour patterns, which are also connected to the economic development stage. To enhance rural India's social and economic growth, the government runs a number of initiatives.

Need for the study

Impact assessment has been a more significant part of development operations in recent years as governments have sought to ensure that funds are being used effectively. Since rural employment programs and institutions have become a vital component of initiatives to fight poverty or promote inclusive development, the focus has shifted to them. Impact evaluation is widely acknowledged as an essential part of the project cycle and is a standard practice in many domains, such as social psychology, environmental and social sciences, and there is increasing evidence of its usage in agricultural research (Margot Bellamy, 2000).

Everybody involved in the project cycle, including donors, legislators, planners, managers, researchers, and end users/beneficiaries, is therefore interested in the project's success or failure and, as a result, in analyzing or assessing its impact. In addition, the Indian government is investing a significant sum of money in MGNREGS, the largest job creation initiative in the world. Different schools of thought on this program contend that MGNREGS benefits agriculture, while others contend that it hinders it by reducing the amount of labor available to the sector.

Objectives of the Study

Examining critically the effects of MGNREGS on a sample of homes in the Vizianagaram area is the primary goal of the study.

1. Analysing the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of the sample respondents in the study area.
2. Assessment of the effects of MGNREGA on the three sample study regions' MGNREGA workers' employment, and Landholdings.
3. To suggest measures that may be useful to the policy makers both at the micro and macro levels for the overall development of MGNREGS.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were employed in the study. The District Water Management Agency, Mandal Revenue Offices, the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, the District Hand Book of Statistics, and the Internet were the sources of secondary data. In order to analyse the effects of the MGNREGS program, the study conducted in-depth research on three mandals in the Andhra Pradesh district of Vizianagaram. Three villages were chosen from each of these mandals based on how well MGNREGS was being implemented. From each village 20 sample respondents and each mandal 60 sample respondents are identified and thus the total respondents covered under is 180. Data are collected from only those respondents who are willing to share the information.

Age Group of the Sample Respondents

The age of the sample respondents is crucial in this scenario as it directly impacts their capabilities. Therefore, research studies relying on primary data should prioritize this factor. Against this perspective in mind, the study aimed to illustrate the Sample Respondents Distribution according to their age.

Table 4.1 presents these details. The highest number of the sample households are in the age group of 31-40 years across in all mandals i.e., Badangi 21(35%), Ramabhadrapuram 16(26.67%) and Makkuva 18(30%). The percentage of the sample households below 30 years of age is very minimal in all mandals in the study area. It is noticed that 30.56 per cent of the sample households are in the age group of 31-40 and 23.89 per cent of them in the age group of 61 & above years in the study area.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Age Group

Age Group (In Years)	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Below 30	4	6.67	7	11.67	5	8.33	16	8.89
31-40	21	35.00	16	26.67	18	30.00	55	30.56
41-50	16	26.67	13	21.66	10	16.67	39	21.66
51-60	7	11.66	9	15.00	11	18.33	27	15.00
61 & above	12	20.00	15	25.00	16	26.67	43	23.89

Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00
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Source: Field Survey

Gender of the Sample Respondents

Table 4.2 presents gender wise Sample Respondents Distribution in the study area. Majority of the sample respondents are females in all the sample mandals. The sample respondents belong to females are reported as 71.67 per cent in Makkuva mandal, followed by 68.33 per cent Badangi mandal and 60 per cent in Ramabhadrapuram mandal. The male respondents on the other hand are 28,33 per cent, 31,67 per cent and 40 per cent respectively. The data clearly shows that, a majority of 120 (66.67%) respondents are female and the rest of 60 (33.33%) are male respondents who are identified for the present study.

Table 2: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Gender

Gender	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Male	19	31.67	24	40.00	17	28.33	60	33.33
Female	41	68.33	36	60.00	43	71.67	120	66.67
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Marital Status of the Sample Respondents

Information relating to Marital Status of the sample respondents is shown in Table 4.3. In all the sample mandals approximately 92 per cent of the sample respondents are married. Unmarried and widow workers are more in Ramabhadrapuram (5% & 6,67%) compared with Makkuva (3.33% & 5%) and Badangi (1.67% & 3.33%) mandals. Majority of the sample households 165 (91.67%) of the respondents are married, 9 (5.00%) are unmarried and the rest of 6 (3.33%) are Widow/Widower who are selected for the present study.

Table 3: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Marital Status

Marital Status	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Married	57	95.00	53	88.33	55	91.67	165	91.67
Unmarried	1	1.67	3	5.00	2	3.33	6	3.33
Widow/Widower	2	3.33	4	6.67	3	5.00	9	5.00
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Caste Category of the Sample Respondents

Caste is also recognized as a significant element in social hierarchy. The caste system holds a strong and enduring position in Indian society. This research categorizes castes into three groups: Other Backward Classes (OBC), Scheduled Caste (SC) and Scheduled Tribe (ST).

Table 4.4 clearly shows that, in Badangi mandal nearly 2/3rd and above of the sample respondents that is 68.33 per cent belong to the caste group of OBC's, followed by scheduled caste 25 per cent, and scheduled tribe (6.67%). Majority of the sample respondents in which 53.33 per cent belongs to OBC's in Ramabhadrapuram mandal while scheduled caste (35%) and scheduled tribe (11.67%) are next in order. In Makkuva mandal a large concentration of sample respondents are OBC's (63.33%) followed by scheduled caste (20%) and scheduled tribes (11.67%). It is observed that, more than half of the sample respondents 111 (61.67%) belongs to OBC's category, followed by 48 (26.67%) of the respondents reported as SC community and the rest of 21 (11.67%) are ST Community respondents who are taken up for the present study.

Table 4: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Caste Category

Marital Status	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
SC	15	25.00	21	35.00	12	20.00	48	26.67
ST	4	6.67	7	11.67		16.67	21	11.67
OBC	41	68.33	32	53.33		63.33	111	61.66
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Religion of the Sample Respondents

Religion stands as one of the most enduring social institutions in human history, representing a crucial aspect of human existence. The distribution of religious affiliations among the participants in the current research is detailed in Table 4.5. The data reveals that 96.67 per cent of the sample respondents belong to the Hindu religious community and only 3.33 per cent belong to the Christian community in Badangi mandal. More than 2/3rd of the sample respondents 88.33 per cent are Hindu's whereas 11.67 per cent are Christians in Ramabhadrapuram mandal. Large number of sample respondents belongs to Hindu religious community (95%) followed by Christians (5%) in Makkuva mandal. Overall, out of 180 sample respondent's majority of the respondents are Hindu religion 168 (93.33%) and the rest of 12 (6.67%) are Christian religion respondents who are taken up for the present study.

Table 5: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Religion

Religion	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Hindu	58	96.67	53	88.33	57	95.00	168	93.33
Christian	2	3.33	7	11.67	3	5.00	12	6.67
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Educational Status of the Sample Respondents

Education significantly influences an individual's status within the society. It plays a crucial role in identifying the opportunities available for securing specific occupations, which subsequently shapes various aspects of life, including health, social status, and job stability. The educational attainment levels of individuals have been categorized into six main groups: illiterate, literate, primary education, secondary education, higher education, and technical education for the purpose of the present study.

According to the data, the illiterate respondents are the highest in Makkuva mandal with 41.67 per cent followed by Badangi mandal with 30 per cent. The illiterate sample respondents are the least at Ramabhadrapuram mandal with 18.33 per cent. The data clearly shows that Primary and Secondary educated respondents are more in Ramabhadrapuram mandal (40% & 41.67%), followed by Badangi mandal (33.33% & 36.67%) and Makkuva (26.67% & 31.67%) in the study area. Overall, the data shows that, 66 (36.67%) of the respondents are qualified in Secondary Education, followed by 60 (33.33%) of the respondents in Primary Education and the rest of 54 (30%) respondents are Illiterates among the selected respondents for the present study.

Table 6: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Educational Background

Educational Status	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Illiterate	18	30.00	11	18.33	25	41.67	54	30.00
Primary	20	33.33	24	40.00	16	26.67	60	33.33
Secondary	22	36.67	25	41.67	19	31.67	66	36.67
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Main Source of Livelihood of the Sample Respondents

Employment is a significant social determinant influencing an individual's economic standing, impacting lifestyle, behavior, conduct, morale, and societal roles. It acts as a measure of socio-economic status and the family's standing. The occupational status of the participants has been categorized into five main groups: cultivators, agricultural laborers, non-agricultural laborers, small business owners, and employees/services.

Data regarding the primary source of livelihood is gathered from the participants and is displayed in Table 4.7. Regarding the occupational distribution among the respondents, the majority are involved in agricultural labor. In Badangi mandal largest proportion of sample respondents are Farm Labour 80, followed by employees/services 11.67, non-farm labour 5 and cultivators 3,33 while these figures in Ramabhadrapuram 73.33, 15, 5, 6.67 and 76.67, 8.33, 10, 5 in Makkuva mandal respectively in the study area. Of the total 180 respondents, 138 (76.67%) of the respondents' main source of livelihood is Farm Labour, followed by 21 (11.67%) of the respondents was employees/services, 12 (6.67%) of the respondents are non-farm labour and the rest of 9 (5%) are owner cultivators in the study area.

Table 7: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Main Source of Income

Source	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Service/ Employees	7	11.67	9	15.00	5	8.33	21	11.67
Cultivator	2	3.33	4	6.67	3	5.00	9	5.00
Farm Labour	48	80.00	44	73.33	46	76.67	138	76.67

Non-farm labour	3	5.00	3	5.00	6	10.00	12	6.66
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Family Size of the Sample Respondents

The size of a family holds significant importance not only for the nation at large but also for the well-being and health of individuals, families, and communities. It directly influences the quality of life experienced by individuals. Quality of life encompasses more than just economic living standards; It extends to a broader spectrum of factors. Family size impacts fundamental human needs, income levels, economic growth, savings, as well as the quality and quantity of food and nutrition. Additionally, it affects land use, urban public systems, health particularly that of mothers and children and education, especially concerning children.

In the present study the respondents have been divided into three categories relating to their size of the family and the data analysis is presented in Table 4.8. The average family size of the total respondents is observed to be 4.5. This is the same for Ramabhadrapuram mandal. The average family size for the other two mandals Badangi and Makkuva is found to be at 4.4 and 4.7 respectively.

The Badangi mandal has the highest share 55 per cent of respondents having 4 & above family members. Looking at the Sample Respondents Distribution by family size in Badangi, we can see that the share of those living as a family with 3 members is (25%), followed by 2 members (11.67%) and those living as a family with 1 member is 8.33 per cent. In Ramabhadrapuram mandal, the percentage of respondents residing with 4 & above

family members is 53.33 per cent, whereas those residing in 3 members category are 26.67 per cent. The percentage of respondents residing in a family with 2 members in this mandal is 15 per cent. In Makkuva mandal, the share of respondents living in 4 & above member category is 53.33 per cent. In this mandal, the share of respondents living in a family with 3 members and 2 members is 33.33 per cent and 8.33 per cent respectively.

The Study clearly shows that 96 (53.33%) of the respondent's family size is 4 & above, whereas 51 (28.33%) of the respondent's family size is three members, followed by 21 (11.67%) of the respondent's family size is two members and the rest of 12 (6.67) respondents are having only one family member who are taken up for the present study.

Table 8: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Family Size

Size of the Family	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	5	8.33	3	5.00	4	6.67	12	6.67
2	7	11.67	9	15.00	5	8.33	21	11.67
3	15	25.00	16	26.67	20	33.33	51	28.33
4 & above	33	55.00	32	53.33	31	51.67	96	53.33
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00
Average Size	4.4		4.5		4.7		4.5	

Source: Field Survey

Family System

The family plays a fundamental role in shaping an individual's socialization process. Further, the family assigns an initial status to the individual before they establish their own status. The type of family a person is a part of has a substantial impact on their personal and social life. For instance, a nuclear family comprises of a single married couple with or without other relatives differs from joint families consist of two or more married couples with or without other relatives. The breakdown of this distribution is outlined in Table 4.9.

An analysis of the family system of the respondents shows that most of the respondents stay in the nuclear family. The share of those staying in nuclear family is 92.22 per cent for total sample. Such share is the highest in Ramabhadrapuram mandal amongst

the selected mandals. The share of respondents residing in nuclear family is 95 per cent in Ramabhadrapuram mandal followed by 91.67 per cent in Makkuva mandal and 90 per cent in Badangi mandal. In the study area the share of respondents residing in joint family is 7.78 per cent. Such share is 10 per cent in Badangi mandal followed by 8.33 per cent in Makkuva mandal and only 5 per cent in Ramabhadrapuram mandal.

Table 9: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Family System

Family System	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Nuclear	54	90.00	57	95.00	55		166	92.22
Joint	6	10.00	3	5.00	5		14	7.78
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Housing Characteristics of Sample Respondents

An observation of housing characteristics of respondents shows that most of the respondents are staying in Pucca houses. The share of those staying in Pucca house is staggering 70 per cent for the entire sample. The share of those staying in semi-pucca house and kutcha house for the entire sample is 24.44 per cent and 5.56 per cent respectively. Most of the houses in the sample have a room size of 3 (64.44%). This is followed by 1-2 rooms with 23.33 per cent and 4 rooms with 12.22 per cent for the entire sample. The other characteristics of the housing shows that most of them have a separate kitchen and toilets in their house. The housing characteristics of sample respondents are shown in Table 4.10.

Table 10: Housing Characteristics of Sample Respondents

Characteristics	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Type of House								
Kutcha	2	3.33	3	5.00	5	8.33	10	5.56
Semi-pucca	18	30.00	15	25.00	11	18.33	44	24.44
Pucca	40	66.67	42	70.00	44	73.33	126	70.00
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Number of Rooms in House								
1-2	14	23.33	17	28.33	11	18.33	42	23.33
3	39	65.00	34	56.67	43	71.67	116	64.44
4	7	11.67	9	15.00	6	10.00	22	12.22
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00
Toilet/Latrine Facility								
Yes	45	75.00	48	80.00	43	71.67	136	75.56
No	15	25.00	12	20.00	17	28.33	44	24.44
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00
Separate Kitchen Room								
Yes	56	93.33	53	88.33	49	81.67	158	87.78
No	4	6.67	7	11.67	11	18.33	22	12.22
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

It is observed that there is a positive sign relating to toilet facility in their houses. About 75.56 per cent of the households having toilet facility and 87.78 per cent of the respondent households having separate kitchen rooms in their houses. This analysis shows that there is every need to improve the economic status of the selected area to achieve the set goals.

Sources of Drinking Water

Water serves as a vital and indispensable resource for humanity. Access to safe drinking water is crucial for the well-being of the entire population. In the study area, of the 180 sample, as many as 95 (52.78%) depends upon piped water, handpump 58 (32.22%), water plant 20 (11.11%) and open well 7 (3.89%) for drinking purpose. Across the three sample mandals, majority of the respondent households are using piped water in Ramabhadrapuram (68.33%), and it is 53.33 per cent in Badangi mandal, whereas handpumps in Makkuva mandal (48.33%) are using water for drinking purpose. The source of drinking water of the sample respondents is shown in Table 4.11.

Table 11: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Sources of Drinking Water

Source	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Piped	32	53.33	41	68.33	22	36.67	95	52.78
Open Well	4	6.67	1	1.67	2	3.33	7	3.89
Hand-pump	16	26.67	13	21.67	29	48.33	58	32.22
Water plant	8	13.33	5	8.33	7	11.67	20	11.11
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Type of Fuel Used

It is observed during the field investigation that the majority of participants utilize LPG as their primary fuel for cooking. Following closely behind is the use of firewood for cooking purposes. The data shows that 61.11 per cent of the respondents use LPG gas whereas 38.89 per cent use firewood as fuel sources for cooking. Across the three sample areas, majority of the respondents are using LPG gas in Ramachandrapuram mandal 39 (65%), while it is in Badangi mandal 37 (61.67%) and Makkuva mandal 34 (56.67%) for cooking purpose. This shows that there are two major sources 'viz' Liquid Petroleum Gas (LPG) and firewood used as cooking purpose in the study area. The source of fuel for cooking purpose is shown in Table 4.12.

Table 12: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Type of Fuel Used for Cooking Purpose

Type of Fuel	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
LPG	37	61.67	39	65.00	34	56.67	110	61.11
Firewood	23	38.33	21	35.00	26	43.33	70	38.89
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Landholding Particulars of the Sample Respondents

The landholdings determine the socio-economic status of the family. In the present study the landholdings have been divided into two categories (Landless and Sharecropper). The landholding pattern of the sample household is shown in Table 4.13. Looking at the landholding pattern of the sample households, it can be found that the ratio of Landless and Sharecropper in Badangi mandal stood at 88.33 to 11.67 amongst the households, while these figures in Ramabhadrapuram mandal are 95 to 5 and Makkuva mandal 91.67 to 8.33 respectively.

It is observed that, above ninety per cent of the sample respondents are landless category 165 (91.67%) and the remaining are Sharecropper category 15 (8.33%) in the study area.

Table 13: Distribution of Sample Respondents by Landholdings

Landholding	Badangi		Ramabhadrapuram		Makkuva		Grand Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Landless	53	88.33	57	95.00	55	91.67	165	91.67
Sharecropper	7	11.67	3	5.00	5	8.33	15	8.33
Total	60	100.00	60	100.00	60	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey

Conclusion:

To sum up, the highest number of sample households is in the age group of 31-40 years across in all mandals i.e., Badangi 21(35%), Ramabhadrapuram 16(26.67%) and Makkuva 18(30%). Majority of the sample respondents belongs to OBCs (61.67%) followed by scheduled caste (26.67%), The field study on the literacy status of the sample respondents shows that the 30 per cent of the respondents are illiterate in the sample area. Majority of the respondents have a family size of 4 & above members. Of the total 180 sample respondents, 138 (76.67%) of the respondents' main source of livelihood is Farm Labour, followed by 21 (11.67%) of the respondents are Service/Employees. The data shows that 61.11 per cent of the respondents use LPG gas for cooking purpose whereas 38.89 per cent use firewood as fuel sources for cooking.

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